

The Role of Channel Migration and Structural Setup in Flood Hazard of Upper Ghaghara River from Bahraich to Faizabad in Uttar Pradesh, India using Geospatial Approach

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Abstract

The upper course of the Ghaghara River in Uttar Pradesh is a very sensitive zone for flooding and the maximum area comes under the influence of high and very high risk zone. Active Flood Plains (AFP) along rivers play a major role in establishing fluvial dynamics. Their association to valley width, channel width, river sinuosity, escarpments and channel migration helps in understanding the physical processes and structural set up in a low dipping monotonous fluvial deposit. The Ghaghara River is one of the dynamic fluvial systems affected by flooding and causing major migrations and channel disruptions in its flow regime.

The present study incorporates the varying channel migration obtained from different spatial and temporal remote sensing (RS) satellite imageries of the upper regime of the Ghaghara River extending from Bahraich to Faizabad districts. The study punctuates the role of monsoonal activity in channel migration, channel width, valley width and prepared a flood hazard zone with the help overlay method through many factors viz. drainage density, soil texture, landuse-landcover (LULC), area of micro watersheds, soil moisture, slope and relief in Geographic Information System (GIS) application based approach. In the study, it is observed that the present stretch of Ghaghara River migrated in NNW-SSE and NNE-SSW in broad flood plains throughout past where the river is deeply entrenched, structurally controlled and provides implications to tectonic setup and climatic inferences by change in sudden deviation and flood situation along the stream flow path of Ghaghara river.

Keywords: Flood plains, Ghaghara River, Remote Sensing, GIS, Channel width, Valley width.

Introduction

Rivers are one of the most important natural sources on earth for their large support to the life and livelihood of living organisms. Many activities such as land use/land cover change, sewage sludge, mine waste, industrial waste, wastewater, atmospheric pollutants, pesticides and fertilizers

are the main activities controlling the quality of river water.^{11,26,38,52} They provide a life for numerous aquatic lives and help in preserving biodiversity. The demand for water for industries and the agriculture sector in India is continuously growing to meet the demands of 1.2 billion people⁴⁴.

Rivers play a dominant role in irrigation, hydropower and recharging the groundwater table, storage of water, purification, shipping and landscape¹⁰. These are the carriers of approximately 37,000 km³ of water and 13.5 x 10⁹ tons of sediment particles to the oceans every year.^{31,34,64}

Ghaghara River and its significant tributaries in Ghaghara megafan are by and large snow-sustained and in charge of flooding occasions each year during monsoon season. However, the high intensity rainfall for a couple of days becomes the essential hotspot for flooding, yet the channel migrations due to high discharge and human interference are additionally similarly contributing their role in flood risks for most recent a very long while. Ceaseless infringement along the stream, recovery of wetlands and water bodies, changes in land use and land cover, deforestation in the upper catchment, development of the thick streets systems are the primary factors that expand the flood likelihood in a region⁵³.

Analysis of river course change from map and imageries information is very helpful to establish the historical stability of the river and their impacts of specific events, either they are natural or human induced. Discharge (amount and variability), sediment load (amount and grain size), width, depth, velocity, slope, bed roughness and bank vegetation density express to oversee the course of channels^{28,32,45,46,48,61}. Each of these is affected by climate, tectonic control and environmental variables such as rainfall, seasonality, temperature and slope.

The river channel migration through time and space is critical to many geomorphological and river management issues^{16,43,65}. This migration of the river channel takes place through the erosion of the channel and controlled by lithology and structural behaviour. Similarly, lateral migration does play an important role in changing the position of channel with the variation of fluid flow and sediment discharge and is associated with bank erosion of the stream bed or channel wall under turbulent flow conditions and can affect locally as well as regionally^{6,17,66}.

Alluvial rivers are inherently dynamic in nature responding to the variation in water and sediment inputs. Alterations in inputs either natural or anthropogenic result in changes in the planform/channel pattern, sinuosity and braiding index.^{24,29,33}

The Ganga basin is also one of the major basins in the global geomorphic context where low dipping landscapes exist and reflect global surface manifestations exhibiting control of both natural as well as structural elements through river channels, escarpments, palaeochannels etc.^{2,13,42,55,60}

The channel related studies like channel width, precipitation induced channel displacements, meandering indices, valley width ratios and entrenchment ratio etc. provide vital information about the changes reflected by channels naturally, structurally or anthropologically. Channel migration depends on the pattern of lithology, structural control, precipitation and urbanization. Time, initial relief, geology and climate are further independent variables that influence the cycle of erosion⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹. Channel migration, channel width and valley width measurements were carried out for the historical approach of river, erosion capability of channel wall and lithological condition of flood plains.

Pooravanchal Gramin Vikas Sansthan (PGVS) and Christian aid published flood situation report dated 15/08/2017 marked Bahraich and Gonda as severely affected flood districts due to Ghaghara River. The reasons are rising floodwater in the downstream area is, heavy rainfall in upstream areas and also the water 1.75 lac cusec discharged by Girijapuri Barrage in Ghaghara River. Therefore, the present study is intended to set up a flood risk hazard map of Upper Ghaghara in Uttar Pradesh performed by weighted overlay analysis (WA) using raster data of the rainfall dispersion, slope, drainage density, land use landcover (LULC), size of micro watersheds and soil texture (Loamy, Sandy and Clayey).

The study aids to elucidate the effect of dynamic channel system in and around the main channel whereby the channel disrupts the natural and anthropogenic activities like agriculture, land use etc. and causes shifts in human practices. This is also showing variation in channel displacement and distance through the interpretation of different temporal and spatial remote sensing data sets and toposheets from 1974 to 2017, the impact of precipitation on channel width and valley width and the response of structural setup in a meandering river system in the low dipping region.

The change in the channel migration also causes fertile soil erosion, embankment failure, agricultural losses etc. during high discharge and responsible for flooding in an area. Thus, the study of the channel migration and their variability on temporal and spatial scale and flood risk zone would render approaches to effective and preventive measures at local as well as global scales.

Study area

Ghaghara River is the major branch of the Ganga River originating from the Mapchachungo glacier in the Himalaya near Mansarowar Lake in the Tibetan mountains at an elevation of about 4800 m.^{36,58} It covers 1080 km of total length in India and is the largest tributary of the Ganga by volume. The Ghaghara River is flowing in NW-SE direction which is almost parallel to the present-day trend of the Ganga plain and Himalayan belt. The Sarju, Sarda, Rapti and Little Gandak rivers are the important tributaries of the Ghaghara River. The Ghaghara valley is very wide ranging between 5–15 km during the monsoon times and during summer it is culminating into about a narrow channel of about 100–200m.⁵³ The geomorphic features of the Ghaghara River comprise the many large, middle channel bars, sidebar, escarpments and flood plains.

The study area of the present investigation lies in between the longitudes 80° - 82° E and latitudes 26° - 29° N and covers 15467 km² area and Lakhimpur-Kheri, Bahraich, Sitapur, Barabanki, Gonda and Faizabad districts in the low lying Gangetic plain (Fig. 1). The low dipping region shows a high development of quaternary sediment by the action of fluvial and Aeolian deposits⁶⁰. The length of the Ghaghara River is about 280 km which covers upper Ghaghara from Bahraich to Gonda districts in Uttar Pradesh. The Sharda, Mana, Terhi and Saryu Rivers are the main tributaries of the Ghaghara River in this region.

Regional Setup of the study area: Geomorphologically, the study area consists of (AFP) Active Flood Plain (T₀), (OFP) Old Flood Plain (T₁) and (OAP) Older Alluvial Plain (T₂) surfaces. The Active Flood Plain Surface (T₀) is located at an elevation of 2–5 m above the river level and contains cut of meanders and sandbars that are dynamic in nature and are reworked during the flood every year. It is often affected by the flood, so this is not suitable for human sustainability but can be used as agriculture. The water reaches almost every year on this plain. It is neither sustainable for settlement nor for agriculture^{5,53,54}.

T₁ is present at 5-10 m above the water level. This contains fluvial terraces and meander scars along the palaeochannels and oxbow lakes which indicate the lateral migration along the palaeochannels, ponds and lakes naturally by over discharge of active flood plain during monsoon. The elevation of T₂ is 10-20 m above the water level and contains various asymmetric palaeochannels. It is made up of high interfluvial areas and free from flooding, sustainable developments and agriculture.

Structurally, the study area represents a number of faults. These faults include the Ghaghara-I and Ghaghara-II along with Barabanki fault, Balrampur-Lucknow fault, Utraula-Amethi fault and some basement high or ridges in Bahraich and Gonda districts that control the flowing path of Ghaghara River.^{36,57,59}

Climatically, the entire basin covers subtropical zone, hence, it experiences good rainfall due to the Indian Summer Monsoon (ISM) that is the great concern for agriculture and in the utilization for natural resources in the area.⁵¹ The temperature varies between 44.4°C and 44.8°C. The average rainfall and evapotranspiration vary between 900mm to 1500mm and 1700 to 1950mm respectively and this variation may be due to differences in the latitude, altitude, humidity, ambient temperature, wind speed, topography and type of flora.

Material and Methods

The standard definition of the limits of a channel bank is based on its normal level of water flow which is often difficult and impractical to extract from remotely sensed data without substantial field calibration^{15,66} but the Remote Sensing (RS) Satellite data have emerged as valuable tool for the acquisition of the holistic picture of an area and grew as the easily approachable data for the study of past channel migration. The channel migration study has been carried out by the manual interpretation of temporal datasets and migration rate shown in table 1.

Along with the RS, geographic information system (GIS) application involves rectification of the Survey of India (SOI) toposheets (1:50,000) in World Geodetic System (WGS-84) and projected into the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) Zone 44 datum in Arc-GIS 10.3. The digitization of the Ghaghara River has been done with temporal datasets of the years 1974, 1980, 1990, 2000, 2011 and 2017 and the migrated length, migration direction and migration rate per year measured in between the two points shown in table 2 and table 3. Migration rate has been calculated by dividing the lateral shifting and the total years in each temporal datasets. The valley width and channel width have also been calculated from ArcGIS 10.3 shown in table 4.

The length of the Ghaghara River from Bahraich to Gonda is ~ 280 km has been measured divided into 10-10 km spot with reference to the toposheet and made it as the base layer for other datasets. In total 28 locations along the Ghaghara River were identified and this proved helpful in the correlation between the shifting of the river, valley width and channel width easily.

Rainfall directly influences the intensity and discharge of streamflow. Rainfall causes flood in Indian rivers during summer monsoon months (June to September) that occur in association with the movement of monsoon depressions and cyclonic storms through the country^{8,9}. Therefore, over most of the Indian region, the rivers carry out almost all the geomorphic work of erosion, transportation and deposition during the summer monsoon season.^{22,55}

To understand the climatic inferences in channel width and valley width, the annual average precipitation data (mm/year) of years 1974, 1980, 1990, 2000, 2011 and 2017

have been taken from India Meteorological Department (IMD) to find out the correlation whether the river channel or valley wall is climatically control or tectonically control. The correlation coefficient was calculated by SPSS software between rainfall, channel width and valley width to find out the climatic role in channel width and valley width.

Kellerhals et al²³ and Rosgen,⁴⁵ describe the entrenchment ratio as the vertical containment of the river and the degree to which it is incised in the valley floor and provides a consistent method for field determination. The entrenchment ratio is the ratio of the width of the flood-prone area to the surface width of the bankfull channel. Therefore, entrenchment ratios have been shown in table 4 calculated by formula:

$$\text{Entrenchment Ratio (Er)} = \frac{\text{Bankfull width surface (W)}}{\text{Mean bankfull depth (D)}}$$

The rainfall data was taken from Indian Meteorological Division (IMD) and was operated for the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) interpolation technique in ArcGIS 10.3 spatial analyst tool. Drainage density was done using stream network produced through SRTM information and preparing has been completed by the spatial analyst tool viz. fill the SRTM-DEM, flow direction of the filled DEM, flow accumulation of flow direction and generated stream network with the help of threshold value (18km²)³⁰. The stream network was further processed by the density tool in ArcGIS for creating a drainage density map of the Ghaghara basin.

The micro-watershed layer was digitized from the stream system dependent on the partitioned stream and the area was determined by geometry tool in ArcGIS. Soil texture has been taken from the georeferenced thematic data from the Bhuwan portal. Flood influenced villages location of the year 2018 was downloaded from Remote Sensing Applications Centre, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh and converted into point data with reference to the World Geodetic System (WGS), 1984 datum in ArcGIS. Flood hazard zonation has been prepared by the overlay analysis of the essential contributing factors like rainfall, slope, drainage density, relief, LULC, size of micro-watershed, soil moisture and soil texture.

Results and Discussion

Shifting of the river channel can be observed at many locations within the stretch of the Ghaghara River and the facies and granulometric analyses suggest that the sand and silt are the principal constituents of the sediment texture in the Ganga Plain.^{14,50,59}

Channel Migration Analysis: Ghaghara River is a major river of central alluvial plains and attains the lowest altitude than other tributaries⁵⁹ and causes channel migration due to flood every year. This is shifting the course of the river as the catastrophic level and affects the landmass and habitation

to a great extent. The present study was carried out from the last 43 years for channel migration of Ghaghara River with migration rate (m/year) and various direction flows around Bahraich to Faizabad district where it is controlled by both natural and structural controls. The following inputs below were helpful in observing the migration distance through temporal data.

Year 1974 to 1980: The channel migration study of the Ghaghara River through Landsat MSS data of the year 1974 and 1980 data in table 2 and fig. 2a noticed that the minimum and maximum migration of the Ghaghara River are 0.17 km with a 28.3 m/year migration rate in the NNE-SSW direction near Nanku Gauri and 2.69 km with 448.33 m/year migration rate NNW-SSE direction near Pirthipur in Bahraich district respectively (Fig. 3a). The Ghaghara River attained more width near Sujauli, Bhadwani (Bahraich), Jarwal, Mustafabad and Tulsipur (Gonda) in 1974 but in 1980 there was no change in width around Dhakia, Bishun, Sujauli and Bhadwani (Bahraich) but the width was decreased in Jarwal, Mustafabad and Tulsipur in 1980.

Year 1980 to 1990: The migration study of Landsat MSS data of the year 1980 and 1990 Landsat MSS data in table 2 and fig. 2b noticed that the minimum migration of Ghaghara River is 0.27 km NNW-SSE direction with 27 m/year migration rate near Ramnagar in Bahraich District and maximum migration was noticed near 4.08 km in NNE-SSW direction with 408 m/year migration rate near Chand Pahia in Bahraich district (Fig. 3b). The river attained more width near about Sujauli and Bhadwani (Bahraich). No change was observed in width around Dhakia, Bishun in 1980 and 1990 but in 1990 width is increased around Purwa Mama in Bahraich and decreased in Sujauli and Bhadwani.

Year 1990 to 2000: Migration study from the Landsat MSS data of the year 2000 and year 1990 Landsat MSS data in table 2 and fig. 2c shows that the minimum migration of Ghaghara River is 0.13 km in the NNW-SSE direction with 13 m/year migration rate around Semra in Lakhimpur - Khiri District and maximum migration noticed near 6.14 km in the NNW-SSE with direction 614 m/year migration rate near Raipur in Faizabad district (Fig. 3c).

There was no recordable migration measurable around Dhakia and Bishun (Bahraich) in the year 1990 and 2000. In 1990, the width was more around Purwa Mama in Bahraich than the year 2000 Ghaghara river channel and maintains average thickness all over the Bahraich and Faizabad districts.

Year 2000 to 2011: The migration study of LISS III data of the year 2011 and year 2000 Landsat MSS data in table 3 and fig. 2d noticed that the minimum migration of Ghaghara river is 0.26 km in the NNE-SSW direction with 26 m/year migration rate around Kaampur in Bahraich district and maximum migration noticed near 6 km in the NNE-SSW direction with 600 m/ year migration rate near Bhadwani in

Bahraich district (Fig. 3d). Ghaghara River in the year 2011 attained more width. There was no change observed around Dhakia and Bishun (Bahraich) in the years 2000 and 2011.

Year 2011 – 2017: Migration study of Landsat MSS data of the year 2017 and year 2011 LISS III data in table 3 and fig. 2e measured that the minimum migration of Ghaghara river is 0.29 km in the NNE-SSW direction with 48.33 m/year migration rate around Argorva in Bahraich District and maximum migration noticed near 5.30 km in the NNE-SSE direction with 883.33 m/year migration rate around Kaampur in Bahraich district (Fig. 3e). The Dhakia and Bishun (Bahraich) do not have observable migrations in the year 2011 and 2017.

Year 1974 – 2017: Migration study of Landsat MSS data of the year 2017 with respect to the year 1974 Landsat MSS in table 3 and fig. 2f observed that the minimum migration of Ghaghara River is 0.16 km in the NNW-SSE direction with 3.72 m/year migration rate around Hardi in Bahraich district and maximum migration was measured 5.36 km in the NW-SE direction 124.65 m/year migration rate around Churria in Faizabad district (Fig. 3f). The noticeable observation here is a comparative study among the years 1974-1980, 1980-1990, 1990-2000, 2000-2011 and 2011-2017, there were no migrations found around Dhakia and Bishun in Bahraich but the channel migration study of 1974-2017 showing 0.54 km migration in the NNE-SSW direction, interprets some highly active tectonic setup or structural controls.

Structural Analysis

Historical approach of many workers suggested a number of studies in different parts of the Ganga Plain which have shown a strong tectonic control on the filling history of the basin.^{2,12,13,20,27,35,41,58,59,62,63,67} Ghaghara fault separates the Ghaghara plain to an upland area and described as Ghaghara I and Ghaghara II faults run towards NW-SE and NNW-SSE. The Balrampur-Lucknow and Utraula-Amethi fault trend northeast-southwest and coincide approximately with the boundaries of the basement Faizabad Ridge⁵⁷ (Fig. 3).

Besides, the lineaments, there are some basement high or metamorphic ridges exhibits over the sedimentary cover. The large basement high or ridges signified by Faizabad ridge around Gonda and Faizabad district and smaller high as Bahraich basement high in Bahraich⁵⁹. These basements highs also reflect the channel morphology and showing a sudden change in the course of the Ghaghara River in Bahraich by Sharda basement and near Faizabad by Faizabad basement ridge.

Entrenchment ratio (Er) is also used to predict the structural setup according to their value range, smaller the Er value, higher the structural controls while higher the range, less the structural control. Er value classified as Entrenched, Moderately Entrenched and Slightly Entrenched based on the value range <1.4, 1.4-2.2 and >2.2 respectively.

Fig. 1: Location Map of the Study Area

Fig. 2a: Migration Analysis of Ghaghara River from 1974-1980

Fig. 2b: Migration Analysis of Ghaghara River from 1980-1990

Fig. 2c: Migration Analysis of Ghaghara River from 1990-2000

Fig. 2d: Migration Analysis of Ghaghara River from 2000-2011

Fig. 2e: Migration Analysis of Ghaghara River from 2011-2017

Fig. 2f: Migration Analysis of Ghaghara River from 1974-2017

Fig. 3a: Showing migration rate from 1974 to 1980

Fig. 3b: Showing migration rate from 1980 to 1990

Fig. 3c: Showing migration rate from 1990 to 2000

Fig. 3d: Showing migration rate from 2000 to 2011

Fig. 3e: Showing migration rate from 2011 to 2017

Fig. 3f: Showing migration rate from 1974 to 2017

Table 1
Following Datasets used in the present study

Data Year	Name	Scale/Resolution
1974	Toposheets (62H/3, 62H/4, 63E/1, 63E/6, 63E/7, 63E/8, 63E13, 63F/9, 63F/13, 63J/1, 63F/5)	1:50,000
1980	Landsat MSS	60m
1990	Landsat TM	30m
2000	Landsat ETM	30m
2011	LISS III	23.5m
2017	Landsat ETM+	15m

Table 2
Showing Lateral Shifting, Migration Rate and Shifting Direction of Ghaghara River

S.N.	1974-80			1980-90			1990-2000		
	Length (Km)	Migration Rate m/year	Direction	Length (Km)	Migration Rate m/year	Direction	Length (Km)	Migration Rate m/year	Direction
FLOW A									
1	No change			No change			No change		
2	No change			No change			No change		
FLOW B									
3	No change			0.74	74	NNW-SSE	1.61	161	NNE-SSW
							1.17	117	NNW-SSE
							1.72	172	NNE-SSW
4	2.69	448.33	NNW-SSE	0.99	99	NNE-SSW	0.13	13	NNW-SSE
				0.56	56	NNW-SSE	1.96	196	NNE-SSW
5	0.33	55.00	NNE-SSW	0.64	64	NNE-SSW	0.28	28	NNW-SSE
				1.29	129	NNW-SSE	1.89	189	NNW-SSE
				1.39	139	NNE-SSW			
6	1.01	168.33	NNW-SSE	1.61	161	NNW-SSE	0.38	38	NNE-SSW
	0.17	28.33	NNE-SSW	1.23	123	NNW-SSE	1.31	131	NNW-SSE
	0.48	80.00	NNW-SSE						
7	0.77	128.33	NNE-SSW	1.32	132	NNW-SSE	2.11	211	NNE-SSW
				0.47	47	NNE-SSW	1.69	169	NNW-SSE
				0.75	75	NW-SE			
8	0.99	165.00	NNW-SSE	1.61	161	NNE-SSW	0.4	40	NNE-SSW
							0.96	96	NNW-SSE
							2.81	281	NNE-SSW
9	1.28	213.33	NNW-SSE	3.31	331	NNE-SSW	0.38	38	NNW-SSE
							0.73	73	NNW-SSE
10	1.23	205.00	NW-SE	2.52	252	NNE-SSW	2.63	263	NNW-SSE
				0.74	74	NNW-SSE	2.89	289	NNE-SSW
11	2.76	460.00	NNW-SSE	4.08	408	NNE-SSW	0.38	38	NNW-SSE
				1.09	109	NNE-SSW	2.14	214	NNW-SSE
12	0.48	80.00	NNE-SSW	2.88	288	NNW-SSE	1.29	129	NNE-SSW
				0.68	68	NNW-SSE			
13	No change			1.53	153	NNW-SSE	2.07	207	NNW-SSE
							4.28	428	NNE-SSW
14	0.87	145.00	NNW-SSE	1.09	109	NNW-SSE	1.25	125	NNW-SSE
							1.72	172	NNE-SSW
15	2.61	435.00	NNE-SSW	1.97	197	NNE-SSW	2.64	264	NW-SE
	1.46	243.33	NNW-SSE	2.27	227	NNW-SSE			
16	No change			0.82	82	NNE-SSW	0.57	57	NNE-SSW
				2.5	250	NNW-SSE			
17	No change			0.27	27	NNW-SSE	0.66	66	NNW-SSE

FLOW C									
18	0.68	113.33	NW-SE	No change		No change	3.26	326	NNE-SSW
19	2.39	398.33	NW-SE	3.25	325	NW-SE	6.14	614	NNW-SSE
20	1.4	233.33	NNE-SSW	2.56	256	NW-SE	1.62	162	NW-SE
21	1.41	235.00	NW-SE	1.95	195	NE-SW	0.84	84	NE-SW
22	0.62	103.33	NE-SW	1.55	155	NW-SE	0.63	63	NW-SE
23	0.33	55.00	NW-SE	3.49	349	SSW-NNE	4.32	432	NE-SW
24	0.4	66.67	NE-SW						
FLOW D									
23	0.36	60.00	NW-SE	1.42	142	NNE-SSW	0.97	97	NW-SE
24	2.32	386.67	NW-SE						
25	0.98	163.33	SSW-NNE	0.83	83	SSW-NNE	1.04	104	NNW-SSE
26	0.67	111.67	SSW-NNE	3.84	384	NNW-SSE	1.69	169	NNE-SSW
27	No change			1.76	176	SSW-NNE	1.16	116	NNW-SSE
FLOW E									
27	0.64	106.67	NW-SE	2.38	238	NNE-SSW	3.26	326	NNE-SSW
28	0.27	45.00	NW-SE				1.61	161	NE-SW
28	No change			0.66	66	NW-SE	1.36	136	NNW-SSE

Fig. 3: Structural Setup of Ghaghara River from Bahraich to Faizabad (Mohan, 2018)

Table 3
Showing the Lateral Shifting, Migration Rate and Shifting Direction of Ghaghara River

S.N.	2000-2011			2011-2017			1974-2017		
	Length (Km)	Migration Rate m/year	Direction	Length (Km)	Migration Rate m/year	Direction	Length (Km)	Migration Rate m/year	Direction
FLOW A									
1	No change			No change			No change		No change
2	No change			No change			0.54	12.56	NNE-SSW
FLOW B									
3	3.33	333	NNE-SSW	0.96	160.00	NNE-SSW	0.82	19.07	NNE-SSW
	0.75	75	NNW-SSE	0.61	101.67	NNW-SSE			
4	1.18	118	NNE-SSW	0.88	146.67	NNW-SSE	4.65	108.14	NW-SE
				0.76	126.67	NNW-SSE			
5	1.46	146	NNW-SSE	0.38	63.33	NNE-SSW	1.61	37.44	NNW-SSE
6	1.37	137	NNE-SSW	0.99	165.00	NNW-SSE	0.58	13.49	NNW-SSE
	1.14	114	NNW-SSE	1.05	175.00	NNW-SSE	0.34	7.91	NNE-SSW
				0.29	48.33	NNE-SSW			
7	1.67	167	NNE-SSW	1.14	190.00	NNE-SSW	0.92	21.40	NNW-SSE
	0.57	57	NNW-SSE	0.61	101.67	NNE-SSW			
8	1.33	133	NNW-SSE	2.32	386.67	NNE-SSW	2.39	55.58	NNE-SSW
	1.52	152	NNE-SSW	1.23	205.00	NNW-SSE			
9	1.99	199	NNW-SSE	1.41	235.00	NNE-SSW	2.06	47.91	NNW-SSE
10	1.71	171	NNE-SSW	1.67	278.33	NW-SE	1.38	32.09	NW-SE
				1.41	235.00	NNE-SSW			
11	3.19	319	NNW-SSE	0.59	98.33	NNE-SSW	3.76	87.44	NNE-SSW
				0.59	98.33	NNW-SSE			
				0.65	108.33	NNW-SSE			
12	0.26	26	NNE-SSW	1.2	200.00	NNE-SSW	0.47	10.93	NNW-SSE
	4.52	452	NNW-SSE	1.33	221.67	NNW-SSE	0.16	3.72	NNW-SSE
							2.63	61.16	NW-SE
13	1.71	171	NNW-SSE	5.3	883.33	NNW-SSE	0.47	10.93	NNW-SSE
	6	600	NNE-SSW						
14	2.24	224	NE-SW	0.68	113.33	NNE-SSW	0.98	22.79	NNE-SSW
	0.94	94	NNW-SSE	0.53	88.33	NNW-SSE			
				1.47	245.00	NW-SE			
15	2.24	224	NNW-SSE	1.74	290.00	NNW-SSE	1.85	43.02	NNW-SSE
				1.61	268.33	NW-SE			
16	0.88	88	NNE[SSW	0.44	73.33	NNW-SSE	0.31	7.21	NW-SE
	2.21	221	NNE-SSW	0.44	73.33	NNE-SSW	2.22	51.63	NW-SE
17	0.36	36	NNW-SSE	0.71	118.33	NNW-SSE	1.71	39.77	NNW-SSE
	1.92	192	NNE-SSW	1.39	231.67	NE-SW	0.57	13.26	NNE-SSW
				1.06	176.67	NW-SE			
FLOW C									
18	0.46	46	NNW-SSE	1.3	216.67	NE-SW	5.36	124.65	SSW-NNE

	2.04	204	NNW-SSE	1.43	238.33	SSW-NNE			
	0.8	80	NW-SE						
19	0.43	43	NW-SE	0.54	90.00	NNE-SSW	1.32	30.70	NW-SE
	1.12	112	NE-SW	0.69	115.00	NW-SE			
20	0.8	80	NW-SE	2.04	340.00	NNE-SSW	2.46	57.21	NNW-SSE
				0.62	103.33	NNW-SSE	1.44	33.49	NW-SE
21	3.8	380	NW-SE	No change		No change	4.21	97.91	NNW-SSE
22	0.54	54	NW-SE	0.41	68.33	NNW-SSE	1.41	32.79	NW-SE
	1.16	116	NW-SE						
FLOW D									
23	1.13	113	NW-SE	0.71	118.33	NW-SE	0.32	7.44	NW-SE
	1.39	139	NNW-SSE	0.77	128.33	NE-SW			
24	2.87	287	NNW-SSE	0.74	123.33	SSW-NNE	1.63	37.91	SSW-NNE
25	1.45	145	NNW-SSE	0.7	116.67	SSW-NNE	0.22	5.12	SSW-NNE
				0.63	105.00	SSW-NNE	1.02	23.72	SSW-NNE
26	1.28	128	NW-SE	0.73	121.67	SSW-NNE	0.79	18.37	SSW-NNE
FLOW E									
27	1.7	170	NW-SE	1.85	308.33	NNW-SSE	3.06	71.16	SSW-NNE
				2.37	395.00	NNE-SSW			
28	0.99	99	NW-SE	0.96	160.00	NNW-SSE	2.45	56.98	NNW-SSE

For entrenched Channel, as the discharge increase, stream full greater than the bankfull increase in depth much faster and slightly entrenched channel reveal as the stream flows greater than the bankfull stage overtops their stream banks and extend onto their floodplain⁴⁵.

The highest entrenchment ratio is 0.25, 0.48, 0.73, 0.58, 1.13 and 0.25 with respect of the temporal datasets of 1974, 1980, 1990, 2000, 2011 and 2017 respectively (Table 5). These low values indicate the channel is deeply entrenched in this region and flowing along with the structural setup. Therefore, the flood approaching by the river is less than climatic influences. The flood condition of any region may depict successfully by the entrenchment ratio. The low entrenchment ratio indicates the channel straightening and favorable situation for flood disaster. It depends on the highwater flow condition during high precipitation as well as human inferences.²¹

Correlation coefficient of channel width and valley width with precipitation: High intensity rainfall plays a very important role in changing the channel morphology as erosion the channel wall, valley wall and lithology contribute with heavy discharge by precipitation as well as transport the eroded material depending on the velocity of river. Channel width and valley with correlation with annual precipitation data in low dipping Ghaghara river system may generate neo-tectonic activity and structural control of the study area (Fig. 4a and 4b).

The correlation notified about channel width show maximum negative correlation (0.57, 0.67 and 0.74) at three

point and maximum positive correlation (0.50) at one point and valley width show negative correlation (0.91, 0.64, 0.52, 0.53, 0.56, 0.59, 0.5, 0.74, 0.73 and 0.54) at ten point and positive correlation (0.65) at one point. The negative correlations indicate channel wall and valley wall are controlled by the strong structural setup. Therefore, the high intensity rainfall and discharge does not affect the channel wall and valley wall during monsoon and causing flood by the overflow of water from drainages.

Flood Hazard Zonation: Flood hazard zone of Upper Ghaghara regime was prepared by overlay method from contributing factors of flood like rainfall distribution (Fig. 5), area of micro-watersheds (Fig. 6), slope (Fig. 7), Relief (Fig. 8) drainage density (Fig. 9), LULC (Fig. 10), soil moisture (Fig. 11) and soil texture as clayey (Fig. 12), loamy (Fig. 13) and sandy (Fig. 14) by using the Equal Interval technique in ArcGIS software³. The rainfall that can't percolate instantaneously in the ground surface streams down through slope as runoff. The runoff water successfully increases the level of water in the river and lakes and overflow water cause flooding.³⁹ The smaller size micro watersheds are more susceptible to flood because micro watersheds with larger drainage areas require a long duration of runoff for a significant increase in water level to become a flood³. A flat and smooth surface is more susceptible to flood because the water does quickly flow and the probability of waterlogging is high while a higher and rough surface can slow down the flood effect²⁵. Drainage density indicates the closeness of spacing of streams and a key detrimental factor for water to travel from source to sink.¹⁹ Drainage density is a backward capacity of infiltration,

higher the drainage density lesser the invasion and hinders the overflow while lesser the drainage density cause higher the infiltration rate and increasingly vulnerable for flooding⁵⁶. Vegetation spread like grassland, forest and crops has considerably more capacity to store water and hinder the precipitation spill over while exposed land and impermeable surfaces, for example, concrete are progressively powerless to flood in light of the fact that these retain no water at all and precipitation overflow is significantly more than vegetation spread.³⁷

The Ghaghara basin has formed due to alluvial deposition with the extreme proportional variation of sand, silt and clay.^{53,54} Sand is more porous and permeable than the silt and clay. The high porous soil attains the highest moisture than less porous soil and less moisture is more probable to flood because of less direct flow (lower runoff).⁷ The soil surface is also a significant factor that gives impact on the flood condition. It controls the measure of water that can penetrate into the soil and hence the amount of water which can flow.⁴⁰

The low infiltration capacity of soil can cause more flood chances on account of the high surface overflow and high soil infiltration can cause slowdown of the flood circumstance. The porosity and permeability of sand are more than the loamy and substantially more than the clayey surface of the soil. In this way, the clayey soil is more defenseless to flood than loamy soil and sandy soil.

Thus, this study based on the contributing factors of the flood hazard zonation map has been prepared (Fig. 15) that indicates almost 50km length along the Ghaghara river flooded over the past (Fig. 16) and maximum upper Ghaghara regime fallen under the high risk zone area (54%) followed by very high risk zone (24%), moderate zone (15%), low zone (3%) and very low zone (2%). Total 171 settlements were affected in year 2018 during monsoon season in which 121 settlements were lying in very high risk zone along the Ghaghara River and 51 settlements were in high risk zone along Sarda river and Ghaghara River.

Fig. 4a: Showing Correlation of channel width (meters) and annual rainfall data (mm/year) of year 1974, 1980, 1990, 2000, 2011 and 2017

Fig. 4b: Showing correlation of valley width (meters) and annual rainfall data (mm/year) of year 1974, 1980, 1990, 2000, 2011 and 2017

Fig. 5: Rainfall Distribution Map of the Study Area

Fig. 6: Micro-watershed Map of the Study Area

Fig. 7: Slope Map of the Study Area

Fig. 8: Relief Map of the Study Area

Fig. 9: Drainage Density Map of the Study Area

Fig. 10: Land use-Landcover Map of the Study Area

Fig. 11: Soil Moisture Map of the Study Area

Fig. 12: Clayey Soil Map of the Study Area

Fig. 13: Loamy Soil Map of the Study Area

Fig. 14: Sandy Soil Map of the Study Area

Fig. 15: Flood Hazard Zonation Map of the Study Area

Fig. 16: Buffer Zone of Flooded Area Map of the Study Area

Table 4
Channel width (Cw), Valley Width (Vw) and Entrenchment Ratio (Er) of Ghaghara River

Spot No.	1974			1980			1990			2000			2011			2017		
	Cw	Vw	Er	Cw	Vw	Er	Cw	Vw	Er	Cw	Vw	Er	Cw	Vw	Er	Cw	Vw	Er
1	0.5	2.17	0.23	0.45	1.06	0.42	0.35	1.88	0.19	0.4	2.21	0.18	0.72	1.53	0.47	0.18	2.04	0.09
2	0.87	3.54	0.25	2.07	4.29	0.48	0.81	2.87	0.28	1.75	3.05	0.58	0.74	3.49	0.21	0.89	3.54	0.25
3	0.66	5.94	0.11	0.22	4.61	0.05	0.52	3.83	0.13	0.31	4.67	0.07	2.15	3.92	0.55	0.36	2.03	0.18
4	0.89	7.08	0.13	0.23	4.87	0.05	0.27	3.75	0.07	0.29	3.53	0.08	3.75	3.62	1.03	0.56	3.18	0.18
5	0.73	3.97	0.18	0.56	1.81	0.31	0.36	2.71	0.13	0.37	2.2	0.17	0.2	2.49	0.08	0.34	4.39	0.08
6	0.99	5.58	0.18	0.12	1.79	0.06	0.4	1.78	0.23	0.33	3.22	0.1	0.63	2.93	0.21	0.43	2.66	0.16
7	0.42	7.98	0.05	0.32	4.24	0.08	0.76	5.04	0.15	0.44	4.73	0.09	0.22	5.64	0.04	0.48	4.33	0.11
8	1.22	6.96	0.18	0.27	2.71	0.1	0.36	3.34	0.11	0.34	2.3	0.15	0.27	4.48	0.06	0.56	3.9	0.14
9	0.73	7.62	0.1	0.27	2.21	0.12	0.43	2.04	0.21	0.3	5.25	0.06	1.72	4.05	0.42	0.4	3.31	0.12
10	0.83	8.7	0.09	0.34	2.99	0.11	1.17	4.36	0.27	0.6	4.84	0.12	1.39	2.66	0.52	0.56	4.93	0.11
11	0.46	10.26	0.05	0.23	3.94	0.06	0.45	8.11	0.06	0.47	4.94	0.1	1.7	5.97	0.29	0.24	7.53	0.03
12	2.18	9.25	0.24	0.33	3.62	0.09	0.62	3.68	0.17	0.4	4.22	0.09	0.31	6.94	0.05	0.28	4.41	0.06
13	1.32	12.96	0.1	0.1	8.21	0.01	0.3	8.2	0.04	0.31	7.2	0.04	0.45	7.65	0.06	0.61	6.65	0.09
14	0.5	8.13	0.06	0.37	5.23	0.07	0.29	4.84	0.06	0.29	3.45	0.08	1.98	3.34	0.59	0.38	4.24	0.09
15	0.3	8.04	0.04	0.26	3.82	0.07	2.41	3.3	0.73	0.26	2.17	0.12	0.55	3.66	0.15	0.25	4.95	0.05
16	0.36	10.8	0.03	0.22	7.33	0.03	0.48	7.56	0.06	0.4	5.14	0.08	0.41	5.26	0.08	0.29	5.41	0.05
17	0.11	9.67	0.01	0.39	4.35	0.09	0.4	4.66	0.09	0.27	2.59	0.1	0.7	2.72	0.26	0.35	2.03	0.17
18	0.64	7.73	0.08	0.39	6.3	0.06	0.29	3.31	0.09	0.5	5.81	0.09	3.92	3.48	1.13	0.67	3.18	0.21
19	0.32	8.21	0.04	0.37	5	0.07	0.43	4.84	0.09	0.34	1.72	0.2	2.29	5.13	0.45	0.44	5.26	0.08
20	0.59	7.42	0.08	0.19	5.17	0.04	0.54	3.68	0.15	0.44	2.59	0.17	0.52	4.1	0.13	0.31	5.22	0.06
21	0.34	6.43	0.05	0.17	1.99	0.08	0.49	2.11	0.23	0.5	3.27	0.15	1.08	1.95	0.55	0.44	2.31	0.19
22	0.42	7.41	0.06	0.34	1.58	0.21	0.53	6.62	0.08	0.28	6.28	0.04	1.44	3.7	0.39	0.31	4.41	0.07
23	0.34	5.43	0.06	0.24	4.38	0.05	0.48	3.31	0.14	0.44	4.78	0.09	0.31	2.53	0.12	0.47	4.93	0.1
24	0.49	6.99	0.07	0.3	2.06	0.15	0.38	1.4	0.27	0.93	4.29	0.22	4.39	2.33	0.89	0.39	5.74	0.07
25	0.87	6.95	0.12	0.32	3.55	0.09	0.59	7.03	0.08	0.56	3.68	0.15	2.06	4.42	0.47	0.3	5.67	0.05
26	1	6.14	0.16	0.43	3.53	0.12	0.7	3.46	0.2	0.28	3.28	0.09	0.57	2.81	0.2	0.28	2.51	0.11
27	0.57	9.8	0.06	0.37	2.19	0.17	0.36	2.98	0.12	0.87	4.82	0.18	1.63	5.92	0.28	0.45	4.23	0.11
28	0.44	7.48	0.06	0.32	2.28	0.14	0.44	1.48	0.3	0.4	3.06	0.13	0.63	4.8	0.13	0.27	4.72	0.06

Conclusion

The flow regimes of upper Ghaghara River were delivered five reaches of channel flow A, B, C, D and E with South to SSE-SSW, NNW-SSE, NW-SE, SSW-NNE from and again obtaining NW-SE direction respectively and maintain this throughout the confluence of the Ganga in Bihar. Flow A is showing 0.55 km lateral shifting in NNE-SSW direction in the last 53 years (1974 to 2017) with a 12.56 m/year migration rate near about Bishun (Bahraich) due to lateral erosion of Bahraich metamorphic basement high present in Bahraich district suggesting deviation of S to SSW-NNE direction.

The flood risk zonation map shows that the upper Ghaghara regime forms an integral part of high-risk zone in flow B and a very high-risk zone in flow C and flow D regime and covered about 25km width along each bank of Ghaghara River over the past. The Ghaghara plain shows mature topography and lateral shifting is much intensive in flow B, C and D during monsoon with NNW-SSE and NNE-SSW courses in the flood plain. The channel is deeply entrenched, controlled by the major faults and basement high and is less affected by the channel wall erosion by the high intensive rainfall. The deeply entrenched channel indicates that the

lateral erosion is less than the deep erosion means channel bed may erode more than the channel wall and stream flows greater than bankfull increases in depth much faster than in width as discharge increases. This stage the flood prone area increases only marginally in width with an increasing flow-stage above than bankfull elevation.

Hence, the present study based on temporal datasets, satellite imageries and flood hazard zonation will be helpful to predict that geomorphic landscapes may largely affect monsoonal variability and tectonic setup in the form of fluvial dynamics.

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